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ARCTIC PASSION

Pan-Arctic Observing
System of Systems:
Implementing Observations
for Societal Needs

Fold

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101003472

Arctic PASSION is contributing to improving the network of observing systems to monitor the environmental changes in the Arctic, working closely with Indigenous and local communities, as well as scientific networks and decision-makers to co-create essential environmental information accessible to support sustainable development and climate change adaptation.

8 Indigenous Communities

35 Partner Institutes

36 Collaborators

Fold

8 Pilot Services

15 Million Euros

17 Countries

4 Years

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